

FREQUENCY AND FACTORS LEADING TO IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA
IN CHILDREN UNDER 2 YEARS OF AGE PRESENTING WITH
HYPOCHROMIC MICROCYTIC ANEMIA AT CIVIL HOSPITAL (LUMHS),
HYDERABAD

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Abstract

Background: Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) remains a major health concern among young children, particularly in low-income settings. We aimed to examine the frequency and underlying factors associated with IDA in children under two years presenting with hypochromic microcytic anemia at a tertiary hospital in Hyderabad, Pakistan.

Methods: We carried out a cross-sectional study involving 174 children aged 1 to 24 months. Caregivers provided sociodemographic and health information through structured interviews, and we assessed iron status using clinical and laboratory findings. We used chi-square tests to explore associations between IDA and key variables, considering p-values below 0.05 as statistically significant.

Results: We found that 39.1% of children had IDA. Children from households earning ≤25,000 PKR per month were more likely to have IDA (p = 0.03), as were those whose mothers had lower levels of education (p = 0.01). Other contributing factors included lack of exclusive breastfeeding, overcrowded households, and history of worm infestation. We did not observe significant associations with age, gender, or place of residence.

Conclusion: IDA affects a substantial proportion of children under two in this setting. Household poverty, maternal education, and preventable health conditions play a central role. Strengthening maternal education, improving early nutrition, and integrating screening and deworming into routine care may help reduce the burden of IDA during early childhood.

INTRODUCTION

Iron deficiency anemia in young children is a widespread public health concern and stands as the most common micronutrient deficiency across the globe [1]. Anemia affects 43% of children aged 6 to 59 months worldwide, with iron deficiency anemia (IDA) accounting for approximately half of these cases. IDA is characterized by a

hemoglobin level below 110 g/L and a ferritin level under 12 µg/L [2-3]. Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) significantly impacts childhood health, contributing to increased mortality and morbidity rates. It is also associated with impaired brain development and diminished cognitive function [4]. Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) is recognized as

the third leading cause of disability worldwide and the 13th major risk factor for global disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) [5]. In Pakistan, the prevalence of IDA among children under five is reported to range between 40% and 70%. [6]

Children are especially susceptible to iron deficiency anemia due to their heightened need for iron during periods of rapid growth, particularly within the first five years of life. Inadequate iron levels during this critical stage can impair cognitive and motor development and weaken the immune system, making them more prone to infections. [7] In developing countries, diets primarily consist of starchy cereals that are deficient in lipids, proteins, vitamins, and essential minerals like iron [8]. Many low-income families, who make up the majority of the population in Pakistan and other similar settings, often lack the financial means to purchase animal-based foods, which are rich sources of highly absorbable iron. [9]

Food insecurity is defined by the lack of access to or availability of sufficient food, leading to both macro and micronutrient deficiencies. In Pakistan, the prevalent food insecurity highlights the economic instability affecting many regions across the country. [10] The study identified a link between maternal iron deficiency anemia and IDA in children, aligning with earlier findings [11-12]. It also emphasizes the high prevalence of IDA among both pregnant and non-pregnant women of reproductive age in Pakistan [13]. A study done by Habib et al found prevalence of iron deficiency anemia to be 33.2%. [14]

Widespread micronutrient deficiencies along with other clinical and social factors are believed to be the leading cause of IDA in Pakistan. However, prevalence data is scarce with many studies more than a decade old or based on small numbers and in small non-representative populations. Further, IDA is best defined as the combination of both low hemoglobin and low ferritin concentrations, whereas the published studies to date from Pakistan are mostly based solely on hemoglobin concentrations. As such, nationally representative robust data are still lacking to determine the socio-demographic factors associated with IDA that will

enable the development of local strategies to treat and prevent IDA in Pakistani children.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Pediatrics, Civil Hospital (LUMHS), Hyderabad, from Nov,01-2024 to Apr, 30-2025. The sample size was determined to be 174 patients, calculated using the WHO sample size calculator with a 33.2% prevalence of iron deficiency anemia, a 7% margin of error, and a 95% confidence level. A non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used to recruit participants. Patients presenting with hypochromic microcytic anemia, confirmed through laboratory findings of hemoglobin ≤ 11.5 g/dl, MCV ≤ 77 fL, and MCH ≤ 25 pg, will be included in the study. Eligible participants were aged from birth to two years, regardless of gender. Exclusion criteria include a history of malnutrition, congenital anomalies, sickle cell anemia, thalassemia, hemophilia, leukemia, lymphoma, or H. pylori infection.

The study commenced after obtaining approval from the hospital's ethical and research committee. All children meeting the inclusion criteria and presenting with hypochromic microcytic anemia at the Pediatric Outpatient Department were enrolled. The purpose and potential benefits of the study was explained to the parents or guardians, and written informed consent was obtained. A brief history was taken, covering demographic information such as age, gender, and place of residence, as well as potential factors contributing to iron deficiency anemia, including maternal illiteracy, number of people in the household, history of exclusive breastfeeding for six months or more, history of worm infestation, and low family monthly income. Blood samples was collected by the researcher under sterile conditions using a 5 ml syringe and sent to the laboratory for iron profile analysis. Patients was classified as having iron deficiency anemia if their ferritin level is below 10 ng/ml and transferrin saturation is below 12%, as defined in the operational definitions. Strict adherence to the exclusion criteria was maintained to minimize bias, and all relevant

information was documented in a pre-designed proforma.

Data analysis was performed using SPSS Version 22. Continuous variables, such as age, hemoglobin, ferritin, iron, MCV, MCH, and the duration of hypochromic microcytic anemia, will be summarized as mean and standard deviation for normally distributed data, confirmed by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, or as median and interquartile range (IQR) for non-normally distributed data. Categorical variables, including gender, place of residence, maternal educational status, family monthly income, maternal occupational status, iron deficiency anemia, and contributing factors, was presented as frequencies and percentages. Effect modifiers were controlled through stratification of age, gender, place of residence, and duration of hypochromic microcytic anemia to assess their influence on the outcome variable. Post-stratification, the chi-square test or Fisher’s exact test was applied as appropriate, with a p-value of ≤ 0.05 considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

A total of 174 children under two years of age with hypochromic microcytic anemia were enrolled in the study. Of these, 119 children (68.4%) were between 13 to 24 months of age, while the remaining 55 (31.6%) were aged 1 to 12 months. Slightly more than half of the participants were female (52.9%), and the majority (83.9%) resided in urban areas. A considerable number of children (63.8%) had experienced symptoms of anemia for more than two weeks prior to presentation.

With respect to socioeconomic characteristics, 44.3% of the families reported a monthly income

of $\leq 25,000$ PKR, and 59.8% of the caregivers were unemployed. Educational attainment varied, with half of the caregivers (50%) having completed secondary education, while 25.9% had higher education and 4.6% were illiterate. Overall, 68 children (39.1%) met the criteria for iron deficiency anemia.

Among the children diagnosed with iron deficiency anemia, 50 (73.5%) belonged to low-income families. Nearly one-third (36.7%) lived in households with five or more members, and 22% had a documented history of worm infestation. Twelve children (17.6%) had not received exclusive breastfeeding during the first six months of life. Maternal illiteracy was present in 11.7% of IDA cases.

When comparing characteristics between children with and without iron deficiency anemia, a statistically significant association emerged with family income ($p = 0.03$). Children from families earning $\leq 25,000$ PKR per month were more likely to have IDA compared to those from higher-income households. Educational status also showed a significant association ($p = 0.01$). None of the children with IDA had illiterate caregivers, yet a higher proportion had caregivers with only primary or secondary education. In contrast, children without IDA were more frequently associated with caregivers who had attained higher education levels.

Other variables, including age group ($p = 0.61$), gender ($p = 0.54$), place of residence ($p = 0.98$), duration of anemia ($p = 0.15$), and parental occupational status ($p = 0.60$), did not show statistically significant associations with the presence of iron deficiency anemia.

Table 1: Distribution of baseline characteristics among the study participants.

Variables	n (%)
Age	
01 to 12 months	55 (31.6)
13 to 24 months	119 (68.4)
Gender	
Male	82 (47.1)
Female	92 (52.9)

Place of residence	
Urban	146 (83.9)
Rural	28 (16.1)
Duration of anemia	
≤ 14 days	63 (36.2)
> 14 days	111 (63.8)
Family monthly income	
≤ 25000	77 (44.3)
> 25000	97 (55.7)
Occupational status	
Employed	70 (40.2)
Unemployed	104 (59.8)
Educational status	
Illiterate	08 (4.6)
Primary	34 (19.5)
Secondary	87 (50)
Higher	45 (25.9)
Iron deficiency anemia	
Yes	68 (39.1)
No	106 (60.9)
Total	174 (100)

Table 2: Distribution of factors leading to iron deficiency anemia (n=68).

Variables	n (%)
Maternal illiteracy	08 (11.7)
Number of people in household ≥ 5	25 (36.7)
History of breastfeeding in six months	12 (17.6)
History of worm infestation	15 (22)
Low family monthly income	50 (73.5)

Table 3: Distribution of patient characteristics according to the iron deficiency anemia groups.

Variables	Iron deficiency anemia (Yes) n (%)	Iron deficiency anemia (No) n (%)	P value
Age			0.61
01 to 12 months	20 (36.4)	35 (63.6)	
13 to 24 months	48 (40.3)	71 (59.7)	

Gender			0.54
Male	34 (41.5)	48 (58.5)	
Female	34 (37)	58 (63)	
Place of residence			0.98
Urban	57 (39)	89 (61)	
Rural	11 (39.3)	17 (60.7)	
Duration of anemia			0.15
≤ 14 days	29 (46)	34 (54)	
> 14 days	39 (35.1)	72 (64.9)	
Family income			0.03
monthly			
≤ 25000	37 (48.1)	40 (51.9)	
> 25000	31 (32)	66 (68)	
Occupational status			0.60
Employed	29 (41.4)	41 (58.6)	
Unemployed	39 (37.5)	65 (62.5)	
Educational status			0.01
Illiterate	00 (00)	08 (100)	
Primary	13 (38.2)	21 (61.8)	
Secondary	42 (48.3)	45 (51.7)	
Higher	13 (28.9)	32 (71.1)	

DISCUSSION:

This study explored the frequency and underlying factors of iron deficiency anemia (IDA) among children under two years presenting with hypochromic microcytic anemia at a tertiary hospital in Hyderabad. We identified IDA in 39.1% of the data. This underscores a moderate yet significant public health burden in this vulnerable age group.[15] Most affected children fell within the 13 to 24-month age range. This period is marked by increased physiological demands and the depletion of iron stores accrued during infancy. [16-17] Despite this trend, our data did not show a statistically significant association between age and IDA. This possibly reflects a uniformly inadequate nutritional landscape across early childhood.

Gender did not emerge as a significant variable, although earlier studies have noted a marginally higher prevalence of IDA among males. This was often attributed to their relatively higher iron requirements during growth spurts. [18] Our findings suggest that shared dietary patterns and living conditions may have diluted any sex-related biological differences in iron status.

Socioeconomic status stood out as a key determinant. Children from households earning ≤25,000 PKR per month had markedly higher odds of developing IDA (p = 0.03). This pattern was consistent with global literature linking poverty to poor diet quality, food insecurity, and limited healthcare access. [19-20] We also observed a protective effect of maternal education. We noted that children whose mothers had

higher education levels were significantly less likely to be iron deficient ($p = 0.01$). This association likely reflects the influence of maternal literacy on child-feeding practices, and health service utilization. [21-22]

While a majority of the sample lived in urban areas, place of residence did not significantly affect IDA prevalence. This aligns with studies from similar contexts where urban poverty replicates the nutritional deficits commonly observed in rural settings. [23] Notably, over 63% of the children had anemia lasting longer than two weeks. This may point to delays in care-seeking or difficulties in recognizing early symptoms. [24]

Among those diagnosed with IDA, several modifiable risk factors were evident. Most lived in low-income, overcrowded households—environments that compromise food availability and sanitation. [25] A substantial proportion (22%) had a history of worm infestation, reinforcing the role of intestinal blood loss in iron depletion. This was comparable to other studies that have been conducted. [26] We also found that nearly one in five children had not been exclusively breastfed during the first six months of life. This is particularly concerning given that early breastfeeding plays a critical role in building neonatal iron reserves and reducing infection risk. [27-28]

Although maternal illiteracy directly affected only a minority (11.7%) of IDA cases, the broader analysis confirmed a strong association between lower maternal education and child anemia. This echoing global findings on the importance of maternal knowledge in shaping child health outcomes. [29]

These findings closely align with large-scale analyses from sub-Saharan Africa, where IDA remains pervasive among children aged 6–23 months. [30] Similar to our observations, that study identified maternal anemia, lack of supplementation, low birth weight, and recurrent infections as leading contributors to anemia in young children. [30-34] It also emphasized the compounding effects of poverty and maternal education on nutritional health. [35]

The intersection of under nutrition and infection emerged as a recurring theme. Frequent illnesses

such as diarrhea and fever disrupt nutrient absorption and increase metabolic demands, often worsening pre-existing deficiencies. [36-37] In settings like ours, these conditions frequently occur alongside poor diet quality, forming a feedback loop that perpetuates anemia.

The consistency of these patterns across different geographic and socioeconomic contexts suggests a shared underlying etiology. Research has shown chronic undernutrition, limited maternal resources, high infectious disease burden, and structural inequities to be the factors involved. [38-41] These interrelated factors reinforce the need for public health strategies that address more than just nutrient supplementation. [42-44]

To effectively reduce IDA prevalence, interventions must operate at multiple levels. Promoting maternal education, supporting exclusive breastfeeding, expanding food fortification, ensuring routine deworming, and improving infection control can collectively reduce the risk of IDA in early childhood. Incorporating anemia screening and nutrition counseling into community-level health services, especially in underserved urban areas, may further improve early detection and management. [45-50]

LIMITATION:

We conducted this study in a single tertiary hospital, so the findings might not fully represent the wider population. Since we used a cross-sectional design, we couldn't establish cause-and-effect relationships between the risk factors and iron deficiency anemia.

CONCLUSION:

Iron deficiency anemia continues to affect a large number of children under two, especially in low-income settings where nutrition and healthcare access are limited. Our study shows that poverty, low maternal education, poor feeding practices, and frequent infections all contribute to this burden. To tackle IDA effectively, we need to go beyond supplements. Thus supporting mothers through education, promoting exclusive breastfeeding, improving household nutrition. Also we need to ensure timely deworming and screening. By focusing on these areas, especially at

the community level, we can make real progress in protecting young children's health and development.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

All the authors declare no conflict of interest.

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AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION:

Collection and acquisition of data & grammatical corrections	Dr. Shahrukh
Concept & design of study & proof read	Dr. Shazia Memon
Drafting the article and finalizing the manuscript	Dr. Kainat
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